

EDUCATIONAL CUBESATS: REMOTE SENSING OF EARTH AND LUNAR SURFACE

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Introduction: This study presents the design and implementation of a 3U CubeSat focused on remote sensing of Earth and lunar surface studies. Equipped with advanced imaging and spectrometric instruments, it aims to monitor environmental changes and analyze lunar composition. The program supports education and capacity

these applications, emphasizing innovative technologies for scientific objectives in challenging environments.

Structure of the CubeSat: The CubeSat is designed in a 3U configuration, balancing payload capacity and power generation. It

Fig. 1: Finite element modeling (FEM)

building while advancing CubeSat technology for future missions. As interest in space exploration grows, there's a need for low-cost, efficient missions by universities and small research institutions. This proposal targets Earth observation and lunar studies [1, 2], leveraging CubeSat technology to gather valuable data on environmental dynamics and lunar geology [3]. The paper discusses the development of a CubeSat for

Fig. 2: Sun-synchronous orbit temperature results: at Full Load (LHS) and Idle Load (RHS).

will conduct two missions: monitoring Earth's land and vegetation spectral signatures and investigating lunar regolith. Structural analysis ensures robustness during launch and extreme lunar conditions, using finite element modeling (FEM) to simulate mechanical loads (Fig. 1).

Thermal analysis addresses temperature cycles during Earth and Moon observations,

employing passive methods to maintain operational ranges. Thermal models from NX

Fig. 3: The maximum power generated during 24 hours.

Space Systems Thermal software ensure temperatures remain within limits (Fig. 2). The payload system consists of two CubeSats—one for Earth observation and one for lunar exploration—equipped with advanced imaging and spectrometric instruments across UV, optical, and NIR bands. The Earth CubeSat will focus on land use and vegetation health, while the Lunar CubeSat will analyze the mineralogical composition, identifying valuable resources like water ice. Power generation is critical for small satellites, so this study optimizes a deployable solar panel array. Using Systems Tool Kit (STK) 12 simulations, we evaluated power generation in various orbits. The design incorporates high-efficiency triple-junction GaAs cells, with rigorous testing of deployment mechanisms. Simulation results indicate an optimized solar panel array generates an average of ≈ 37 W over one day, crucial for energy-dependent payloads in LEO and lunar conditions (Fig. 3).

Lunar Rover: The system consists of an aluminum chassis, modular CubeSat structure, independently driven wheels for mobility on the lunar surface, deployable solar panels for power generation, and an on-board camera payload for surface imaging and navigation. The entire system has been co-designed to ensure compatibility and reliability from launch conditions until lunar surface operation, resulting in an estimated CubeSat mass of 4.0 kg and a total CubeSat-based rover mass of 5.0 kg.

Conclusion: This study highlights the feasibility and advantages of an optimized deployable solar panel array for CubeSats operating in LEO and lunar orbit. The design enhances power generation and mission longevity, making it suitable for extended deep-space operations. As part of the LUNEX and EuroMoonMars initiatives, this research also explores the potential of CubeSat-based rovers for lunar surface exploration. The results demonstrate that a

Fig. 4: CubeSat-Based Rover Design

CubeSat-based rover can meet the requirements for small-scale lunar missions, offering a cost-effective alternative to traditional exploration methods (Fig. 4).

Acknowledgement: We would like to express his heartfelt appreciation to EuroSpaceHub and LUNEX EuroMoonMars Earth Space Innovation for their generous funding and unwavering support.

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